

Electrospun PVA/PVP/Pectin Nanofibrous Patches Loaded with Hawthorn and Dragon's Blood for Synergistic Wound Care

Moein Zarei¹, Jakub Trzciński¹, Dominik Baraniecki¹, Paulina Trzaskowska¹, Mustafa Alsarraf¹, Monika Staniszewska¹, Jagan Mohan Dodda², Tomáš Kovářik^{2,3}, Jaeyun Kim⁴, Ewa Kijewska-Gawrońska^{1*}

¹*Centre for Advanced Materials and Technologies CEZAMAT, Warsaw University of Technology, Warsaw, Poland.*

²*New Technologies – Research Centre (NTC), University of West Bohemia, Pilsen, Czech Republic*

³*Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, University of West Bohemia, Pilsen, Czech Republic*

⁴ *Sungkyunkwan University, Suwon, South Korea*

**Corresponding author: ewa.kijenska@pw.edu.pl*

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Abstract

With the rising occurrence of skin diseases such as atopic dermatitis (AD), which are often associated with inflammation, skin barrier damage and related complications, there is an urgent need for simple and effective early-stage treatment strategies. Although current therapies, including moisturizers, injections, and corticosteroids, offer some relief, they present limitations such as side effects, high cost, or limited efficacy. Therefore, developing a straightforward therapeutic patch that promotes skin regeneration and enables efficient drug delivery is essential. In this study, electrospun nanofibrous patches composed of polyvinyl alcohol (PVA), polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP), and pectin (PEC) were fabricated and loaded with Hawthorn Extract (HE) and Dragon's Blood (DB) to enhance wound healing capacity. The patches were comprehensively characterized by morphological, chemical, and functional analyses. Surface wettability, swelling, and *in vitro* release studies confirmed improved hydrophilicity, rapid fluid uptake and sustained delivery of the plant extracts. Antifungal activity against *Candida albicans* showed that dual-extract patches completely inhibited fungal growth, while cytotoxicity assays with L929 fibroblasts confirmed biocompatibility. *In vivo* skin hydration testing on human volunteers demonstrated significant improvements, with dual-extract patches enhancing skin moisture by up to 44% over a 6-hour period compared to the control group. These findings indicate that electrospun PVA/PVP/PEC patches, particularly those incorporating both HE and DB, combine hydration, antifungal properties and biocompatibility. Such features highlight their strong potential for translation into clinical studies for treating AD and related chronic skin conditions.

Keywords:

Atopic dermatitis, electrospinning, polyvinyl alcohol, Hawthorn Extract, Dragon's Blood, Antifungal

Introduction

Atopic dermatitis (AD) is a chronic, inflammatory skin condition that affects millions worldwide. Characterized by dry, itchy, and inflamed skin, AD significantly impacts patients' quality of life, often leading to sleep disturbances, social stigma, and psychological distress[1]. Current treatments for AD include topical corticosteroids, calcineurin inhibitors and emollients, which provide symptomatic relief but do not address the underlying causes or prevent secondary infections [2]. Moreover, prolonged use of corticosteroids can lead to adverse side effects such as skin atrophy, striae, and systemic absorption, necessitating alternative therapeutic approaches. The prevalence of fungal colonization in AD lesions, particularly *Candida spp.*, further complicates treatment, with multiple studies reporting a higher abundance of *Candida* in AD skin (especially in severe disease and flexural sites), which can aggravate inflammation and impair barrier function[3,4]. Antifungal resistance and biofilm-associated tolerance in *Candida* are emerging concerns, underscoring the need for localized, sustained antifungal delivery rather than short-contact creams[5]. In this context, advanced wound dressings loaded with antifungal agents (e.g., ketoconazole, clotrimazole, amphotericin B) or natural bioactives provide a comfortable, breathable platform that maintains moisture balance while delivering prolonged anti-*Candida* activity at the lesion site[6–8]. These dressings can deliver localized therapy, minimizing systemic side effects while providing a physical barrier against external pathogens. Different approaches for wound dressing have been employed to address these challenges, including using hydrogels, foams, and films.

Recent advancements include multifunctional dressings that target multiple endogenous repair mechanisms, incorporating nanofibers, functional nanoparticles and bioactive substances[9,10]. Electrospun nanofibers are promising candidates for wound dressings due to their high surface area, porous structure and drug incorporation capability, and tunable mechanical properties, which enable them to protect wounds from infections and initiate the healing process[11]. By applying high voltage to a polymer solution, ultrafine fibers form and collect on a grounded surface[12]. Electrospun nanofibers' porous structure creates an environment conducive to wound healing by supporting oxygen and nutrient exchange, promoting cell growth, and facilitating the delivery of bioactive molecules[13]. The versatility of electrospinning enables the use of a wide range of polymeric materials, allowing for customization based on specific application needs, and the incorporation of various therapeutic agents, such as antibiotics, anti-fungal, and anti-inflammatory drugs, directly into the nanofiber matrix[14]. For instance, electrospun gellan/PVA nanofibers loaded with cinnamaldehyde showed potent anti-*Candida* activity, supporting their use as antifungal wound dressings[15]. Similarly, propolis-loaded PLGA electrospun nanofibers produced clear inhibition zones against *C. albicans* while remaining fibroblast-biocompatible and supporting *in-vitro* wound closure in scratch assays[16].

Commercial wound dressings are manufactured from a variety of natural and synthetic materials tailored to different wound types and healing needs. Traditional dressings often use cotton, gauze, cellulose or synthetic fibres, while modern advanced dressings are made from polymers such as polyurethane, hydrocolloids, hydrogels, foams, alginates, and other biocompatible polymers that help maintain moisture balance and protect the wound environment[17]. Polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) and polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP) are versatile synthetic polymers widely used to fabricate electrospun fibers for biomedical applications due to their biocompatibility, biodegradability, and low cytotoxicity[18,19]. PVA-based wound dressing materials have been extensively studied due to their ability to maintain a moist wound environment, which is crucial for faster healing[20]. Additionally, PVA can be easily blended with other bioactive polymers (e.g., chitosan, gelatin, or pectin) to enhance antimicrobial activity, mechanical properties, and bioactivity[21,22]. PVA/PVP blends have shown promising results in overcoming the limitations of individual polymers, offering improved mechanical properties and bacterial barrier performance[23]. Pectin

(PEC), a natural polysaccharide derived from agricultural waste, is attractive for wound dressings due to its film-forming capacity, hydrophilicity, biocompatibility, and biodegradability[24]. Recent studies have shown that the addition of PEC into electrospun nanofibers demonstrated improved hydrophilicity and degradability, suitable for sustained drug release in wound dressings[25,26]. The combination of PVA, PVP, and PEC in electrospun nanofibers leverages the synergistic advantages of each polymer, creating a multifunctional scaffold tailored for AD treatment. Despite their excellent biocompatibility, a major challenge in using hydrophilic polymers like PVA, PVP, and Pectin for wound dressings is their high solubility in aqueous environments, which can lead to rapid structural disintegration upon contact with wound exudate[27]. Therefore, chemical or physical crosslinking is essential to ensure structural integrity and functional longevity. Crosslinking mechanisms, such as those utilizing glutaraldehyde vapor[27,28], facilitate the formation of a stable three-dimensional network by creating chemical bridges between polymer chains. This process not only improves the mechanical stability and tensile strength of the nanofibers but also regulates the swelling behavior and degradability, thereby enabling a controlled and sustained release of the incorporated bioactive agents. Consequently, optimizing the crosslinking duration is a critical step in balancing the water-stability of the patch with its flexibility and therapeutic performance.

The incorporation of natural antimicrobial agents into wound dressings addresses the growing concerns regarding antifungal resistance and the need for safer, more effective therapies. Numerous studies have explored the potential of herbal extracts and traditional medicines as alternatives to conventional treatments. For example, propolis, tea tree oil, and curcumin have been extensively investigated for their antifungal, anti-inflammatory, and wound-healing properties and have been incorporated into wound dressings and electrospun fibers to enhance their therapeutic efficacy[16,29,30]. However, the search for novel bioactive compounds continues to expand the repertoire of available options. Plant-based materials such as Dragon's blood, derived from the red resin of *Dracaena cinnabari* trees, have garnered attention for their potent antimicrobial and wound-healing activities. Traditional medicine has long utilized dragon blood for treating various skin diseases and wound healing[31]. Regarding the direct anti-*Candida* activity of Dragon's blood, aqueous and methanolic resin extracts inhibited *Candida albicans* with zones of inhibition comparable to miconazole *in vitro*[32]. Likewise, hawthorn (*Crataegus* species) extract produced concentration-dependent inhibition of *C. albicans*, its use as a natural antifungal for oral/skin applications[33]. Studies have demonstrated that hawthorn extract can accelerate wound healing by modulating inflammatory responses and enhancing cellular proliferation[34]. The novelty of combining dragon blood and hawthorn extracts in electrospun nanofibers lies in their complementary mechanisms of action and the synergistic effects they produce. Previous research has highlighted the potential of incorporating multiple bioactive agents to achieve enhanced therapeutic outcomes[35]. Based on this data, combining bioactive agents within electrospun dressings is a rational strategy. Combination payloads in electrospun patches have already shown stronger, longer anti-*Candida* effects than single agents, underscoring the potential for synergistic antifungal delivery at the lesion site[36].

The primary objective of this study is to develop and characterize electrospun nanofibers composed of PVA, PVP, and PEC, loaded with dragon blood and hawthorn extracts, as a wound dressing for the potential treatment of AD-associated infections. Through systematic experimentation, we seek to optimize the electrospinning parameters to produce nanofibers with desirable morphological, mechanical, and biological properties. The efficacy of the developed wound dressings will be evaluated *in vitro* using fungal cultures and fibroblast cells, assessing their antifungal activity, cytotoxicity, and wound-healing potential.

Materials and methods

Materials

Polyvinyl alcohol (Mw 89-98 KDa, 99+% hydrolyzed, CAS No. 9002-89-5), pectin from apple (CAS No. 9000-69-5), and polyvinylpyrrolidone (Mw 1300 KDa, CAS No. 9003-39-8) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich, USA. Dragon's Blood hydroglycolic extract (*Croton lechleri* resin, s extract – Propanediol, CAS: 504-63-2),; Water, CAS: 7732-18-5, *Croton lechleri* Resin Powder, CAS: 999999-99-4) and Hawthorn extract (Aqua & *Crataegus oxyacantha* Stem Extract), CAS: 84603-61-2, were purchased from Esent.pl - Studio Talarczyk, Szczecin, Poland.

Electrospinning

The electrospinning process involved multiple steps, starting with dissolving PVA in distilled water at 80°C, with continuous stirring for 1 h to ensure complete dissolution. Once the PVA was fully dissolved, PVP was added to the solution, and the mixture was stirred for 24 h to achieve homogeneity. In parallel, PEC was separately dissolved in distilled water by stirring at room temperature for 24 h. After both solutions were prepared, the PVA-PVP solution was combined with the PEC solution and stirred for an additional 1 h at room temperature to form the final electrospinning solution. Before the addition of natural bioactive agents, the electrospinning parameters were systematically optimized to achieve optimal fiber morphology and mechanical properties. Relative humidity levels were maintained between 35% and 45%, and ambient temperatures were maintained around 22°C to prevent premature drying or condensation on the fibers. The total polymer concentration of this formulation was optimized at 15% w/v, with a PVA:PVP:PEC ratio of 70:20:10. Following the optimization of the polymer solution, natural bio-active components were introduced into the blend. DB and HE were added at a concentration of 70% v/w, based on the total mass of the polymers. The addition of these compounds together was performed in five different configurations: **1)** PVA-PVP-PEC (P0) blend without any agent (No Drug); **2)** PH: HE was added to the PVA-PVP-PEC blend at a concentration of 70% v/w. **3)** PD: DB was added to the PVA-PVP-PEC blend at a concentration of 70% v/w. **4)** PHD-M: Both HE and DB were mixed together into the PVA-PVP-PEC blend at a concentration of 70% v/w each. **5)** PHD-Co: HE and DB fibers were collected in a co-spinning set up, each extract was incorporated into a separate solution at a concentration of 140% w/v. Because the electrospinning time was halved (to maintain the same thickness and surface area coverage), the drug concentration in the spinning solution needed to be doubled, resulting in a total of 140% w/v each. Using a dual-syringe and dual-needle setup enabled by the electrospinning device, the two solutions were co-spun simultaneously.

Crosslinking Procedure

The electrospun fibers were crosslinked in a closed chamber at 40°C, using glutaraldehyde (GA) vapor at 25% concentration. The crosslinking process was conducted over varying time periods (1–6 h) to optimize it according to the stability and shrinkage of the patches. Based on preliminary solubility and shape retention tests in contact with water, the 4-hour period was selected as the optimum crosslinking duration. To provide a clear visual overview of the experimental design, the complete fabrication workflow, from polymer dissolution and drug incorporation to electrospinning and crosslinking, is summarized in Figure 1. While SEM and FTIR were performed on both crosslinked and non-crosslinked fibers to evaluate the effects of the crosslinking, all subsequent characterizations and biological assays were conducted exclusively on the optimized 4-hour crosslinked samples.

Figure 1. Schematic illustration of the fabrication workflow for the electrospun nanofibrous patches. The process depicts the preparation of the PVA/PVP/PEC solution, the electrospinning setup, and the subsequent vapor crosslinking treatment with glutaraldehyde.

Fiber morphology

The morphology of the electrospun patches was examined using scanning electron microscopy (SEM). To enhance surface conductivity, the patches were sputter-coated with a thin gold-palladium (80:20) layer using a sputter coater (Quorum Q150T). The coated patches were then imaged using a Hitachi SU-8230 SEM device. Images were acquired at an accelerating voltage of 15 kV and at various magnifications (from 1000x to 20,000x) to assess both the overall structure and the fiber morphology. Fiber diameter measurements were performed on the obtained SEM micrographs using ImageJ analysis software by measuring 50 individual fibers, which were randomly selected from multiple images for each sample, to determine the average fiber diameter and its distribution.

Chemical Properties

The chemical composition and the presence of characteristic functional groups within the electrospun patches were analyzed using Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR). Spectra were recorded using a Nicolet iS50 FT-IR, Thermo Scientific. Spectra were collected over a wavenumber range of 4000 to 400 cm^{-1} and 32 scans per sample. Data analysis was performed using the instrument's software (Thermo Scientific OMNIC software). Characteristic peaks corresponding to the functional groups of the patch components were identified by comparison with literature values and spectral databases.

Mechanical Properties

The mechanical properties of the electrospun patches were evaluated through uniaxial tensile testing using an Instron 5943 Universal Testing Machine. Samples were prepared by cutting the electrospun mats into rectangular strips with specific dimensions of 30 × 10 mm and an average thickness of 0.4 mm. The thickness of each sample was measured at multiple points using a digital micrometer prior to testing, and the average thickness was used for cross-sectional area calculations. The tensile tests were conducted at room temperature under ambient conditions using a 50 N load cell with a constant crosshead speed of 1 mm/min, and displacement data were recorded throughout the test until break. At least 3 samples for each patch type were tested and the results were expressed as the mean ± standard deviation.

Thermal Analysis

Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) measurements were carried out with a Q200 calorimeter (TA Instruments) under a nitrogen purge of 40 ml min⁻¹. Approximately 5 mg of each nanofibre sample was sealed in a Tzero hermetic aluminium pan. The specimens were heated from 30°C to 200°C at 10°C min⁻¹, cooled to 30°C at the same rate, and then subjected to a second heating run up to 500°C to remove residual moisture. The degree of crystallinity was calculated from the DSC thermograms using the melting enthalpy (ΔH_m) according to the equation:

$$\text{Crystallinity (\%)} = (\Delta H_m / W \Delta H_m^0) \times 100 \quad (1)$$

Where W is the weight fraction of PVA, ΔH_m^0 is the theoretical enthalpy of 100% crystalline PVA (138.6 J/g)[37].

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was assessed on a Q500 thermogravimetric analyzer (TA Instruments, USA). Samples of about 5 mg were heated from 30°C to 800°C at 10 °C min⁻¹ under a nitrogen atmosphere. TGA and derivative weight-loss curves were recorded for all formulations. Dynamic thermal mechanical analysis (DMA) was performed using a DMA Q800 (TA Instruments, USA) in tensile mode. Rectangular strips 6 mm wide and 450 ± 50 µm thick were prepared from each electrospun mat and mounted between film clamps with a 15 mm gauge length. Storage modulus (E'), loss modulus (E'') and tan δ were collected as a function of temperature.

Water Contact Angle

Water contact angles were measured using a Data Physics OCA 15EC goniometer. A 2 µl droplet of deionized water was dispensed onto the sample surface at a rate of 1 µl/s, and the droplet profile was captured using a high-resolution camera. Measurements were performed in a controlled environment (25 ± 1°C, 40 ± 5% relative humidity), and the average contact angle and standard deviation were calculated from three repeated measurements at different locations on each sample.

Swelling Ratio

The swelling behavior of the electrospun patches was evaluated by immersing weighed samples in distilled water at room temperature for different periods of time: 15 min, 30 min, 1 h, 2 h, 4 h, 8 h, 24 h, 48 h and 72 h. Patches samples were cut into 10 × 10 mm and their initial dry weights were accurately measured. These samples were then fully immersed in 4 ml of distilled water, and at predetermined time points, the samples were collected from the swelling medium. Excess surface liquid was gently blotted away using filter paper to ensure only the absorbed liquid remained. The weight of the swollen samples was then immediately measured using the same analytical balance. The swelling ratio (SR) was calculated using the following equation:

$$SR = W_d W_s / W_d \quad (2)$$

where: W_d is the initial dry weight of the patch and W_s is the weight of the swollen patch at a specific time point. The swelling ratio was typically measured with 3 sample repetitions for each patch type, and the results were expressed as the mean \pm standard deviation.

Degradation Study

The *in vitro* degradation of the electrospun patches was assessed by monitoring the mass loss of the patches over time when immersed in a simulated physiological environment. The degradation medium used was phosphate-buffered saline (PBS, pH 7.4) maintained at a temperature of $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$, under an orbital shaker with a rotating speed of 100 rpm. The patch samples were cut into circular pieces with a diameter of 1 cm, and their initial dry weights (W_0) were accurately measured (5 ± 0.3 mg) using an analytical balance with 0.1 mg accuracy. These samples were then individually immersed in 2 ml of degradation medium and placed on an orbital shaker. The degradation medium was refreshed at 30 min, 1, 4, 8, 24, 48, and 72 h, and the samples were carefully removed from the degradation medium. Any remaining degradation products or salt precipitates on the patch surface were gently rinsed off with distilled water and the patches were then dried to a constant weight in a vacuum oven at room temperature for 72 h, and their final dry weights (W_d) were recorded. The mass loss (%) at each time point was calculated using the following equation:

$$\text{Mass Loss (\%)} = (W_d - W_0) / W_0 \quad (3)$$

where: W_0 is the initial dry weight of the patch, and W_t is the dry weight of the patch after immersion for a specific time period. The experiment was conducted with 3 repetitions, and the results were expressed as the mean \pm standard deviation.

Drug Release Study

To evaluate the release kinetics of the antifungal agents from the electrospun fibers, an *in vitro* drug release study was conducted. A known weight of the drug-loaded patch in a circular piece with a diameter of 10 mm weighing 5 mg (± 0.3 mg) was immersed in 4ml of phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) at 37°C , under an orbital shaker with a rotating speed of 100 rpm. At predetermined time intervals (0, 3, 6, 9, 24, 48, 72, 96, and 120 h) the release medium was withdrawn and immediately replaced with an equal volume of fresh release medium to maintain a constant volume. The withdrawn samples were prepared by transferring 500 μl to a quartz cuvette with a 1 cm path length. UV-Visible absorption spectra were recorded at room temperature using the Jasco V-700 spectrophotometer (measurement range: 190–600 nm; 1000nm/min). Prior to each measurement, a blank sample containing pure solvent (PBS) was used for baseline correction. Absorbance values were obtained in triplicate for each sample, and the results were expressed as the mean \pm standard deviation. Quantitative analyses were performed according to the Beer-Lambert law calibration curve for both extracts, with $R^2=0.99295$ for the 295 nm hawthorn extract and $R^2=0.99943$ for the 331 nm dragon blood extract.

Antifungal Activity Study

The antifungal activity of the electrospun patches was evaluated against *C. albicans* using two complementary assays: a qualitative fungistatic inhibition zone test and a quantitative fungicidal growth reduction and recovery test. For the fungistatic assay, patches were placed on YEPD agar plates inoculated with a standardized suspension of *C. albicans* (approximately 10^6 colony-forming units CFU/ml) to form a uniform lawn. The plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 h, and the zones of inhibition around each patch were visually assessed and photographed to determine the extent of fungal growth suppression. For the fungicidal assay, patches from the fungistatic study were transferred to 20 ml YEPD broth in Falcon tubes and incubated with shaking for 2 h at 37°C . Following incubation, the suspension was serially diluted

10,000 times, and 100 μ l aliquots were spread onto YEPD agar plates. After 24 h of incubation at 37°C, CFUs were enumerated for both treated and control samples. The fungicidal effect was quantified as decimal log reduction using the formula: $\log R = \log_{10}(\text{CFU/ml control}) - \log_{10}(\text{CFU/ml treated cells})$. A $\log R \geq 3$ was defined as fungicidal activity. Experiments were performed in triplicate across three independent runs, with data presented as means.

Cytotoxicity Study

To evaluate the potential cytotoxicity of the electrospun patches, an indirect extract-based cytotoxicity test was conducted in accordance with ISO 10993-5 and 10993-12 standards[38]. using the L929 mouse fibroblast cell line, and patch extracts were prepared based on the surface-to-volume ratio of 6 cm^2/ml . The samples were sterilized by ultraviolet (UV) irradiation, exposing each side to UV light for 30 min under aseptic conditions. Sterilized samples were then placed in complete growth medium and incubated on a shaker at 37°C in a humidified CO_2 incubator for 72 h to allow the release of potential leachables. L929 fibroblast cells were seeded into a 96-well culture plate at a density of 1×10^4 cells/well in complete Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM), supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS), 2 mM L-glutamine, 100 U/ml penicillin, and 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ streptomycin. After 24 h of initial cell attachment, the culture medium was replaced with 100 μ l of the corresponding filtered patches' extract. A 0.01% Triton-X solution in medium served as the positive control and complete medium as the negative control. Following 24 h of exposure to the extracts and controls, cell metabolic activity was assessed using the MTT assay. Ten microliters of 5 mg/ml MTT solution in medium was added to each well and incubated for 4 h at 37°C. Formazan crystals formed by metabolically active cells were then solubilized using 10% SDS in water and absorbance was measured at 570 nm using a microplate reader (6 readings per extract). Cell viability was expressed as a percentage relative to the negative control, with values higher than 70% considered non-cytotoxic according to ISO 10993-5. Each test condition was repeated three times in technical replicates.

Water Vapor Transmission Rate (WVTR)

The water vapor transmission rate (WVTR) of electrospun patches was measured following the ASTM E96/E96M-16 desiccant method with slight modifications[39]. The developed test setup consisted of 15 ml Falcon tubes partially filled with pre-dried silica gel, used as a desiccant to absorb moisture passing through the patch. The electrospun patch samples were cut to fit the opening of the Falcon tubes (inner diameter: 1.5 cm; exposed area = $1.767 \text{ cm}^2 = 0.0001767 \text{ m}^2$). Each patch was carefully sealed over the tube opening using parafilm, ensuring vapor-tight edges to prevent side leakage. The entire assembly (tube, silica, and patch) was weighed using an analytical balance (accuracy: 0.1 mg) to obtain the initial weight. The prepared tubes were then placed upright inside a humidified chamber, created by placing an open reservoir of distilled water in a sealed container. The chamber was maintained at a constant temperature of $32 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ using a laboratory oven, simulating skin surface temperature. Weight measurements were recorded at 24, 48, and 72 h, and the cumulative weight gain was attributed to water vapor permeation through the patch. A separate control setup without silica gel was tested to assess and correct for any water absorption by the patch material itself. However, this contribution was found to be negligible for the presented data.

The WVTR was calculated using the following equation:

$$\text{WVTR} = \Delta W / A \cdot T \quad (4)$$

Where ΔW is the weight gain due to water vapor transmission (g), A is the exposed surface area of the patch (m^2), and T is the time of exposure (days). All measurements were conducted in triplicate, and the mean values were used for analysis.

Skin Hydration Study

The skin hydration efficacy of the electrospun nanofibrous patches was evaluated using a non-invasive skin moisture analyzer under standardized environmental conditions. The study was conducted in an environment maintained at $25 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ and $40 \pm 5\%$ relative humidity to ensure consistency in measurements. A total of seven healthy adult volunteers (both male and female), representing diverse skin types and ethnic backgrounds from Asia, the Middle East, Europe, and Africa, participated in the study. All participants had normal to mildly dry skin and provided informed consent in accordance with institutional ethical guidelines. Electrospun patches were cut into $1.5\text{ cm} \times 4\text{ cm}$ strips and stored in a vacuum desiccator before testing to prevent premature moisture absorption. Skin hydration was assessed on the inner forearm of each participant. Baseline moisture content was measured at three designated points using a calibrated skin moisture analyzer. Each test site was then covered with a specific patch variant and fixed in place by using medical-grade adhesive tape on the edges of the samples. Skin hydration measurements were recorded at three time points: 0 h (pre-application), 3 h, and 6 h post-application. Each measurement was performed in triplicate for each time point and patch type per participant. The mean values and standard deviations were calculated to assess the hydration effects across all formulations. The human skin testing reported in this study followed established ethical principles for cosmetic testing (EU Council Directive 76/768/EEC) and the World Medical Association Declaration of Helsinki, consistent with established precedents for the non-invasive evaluation of nanofibrous patches[40,41]. All procedures were explained to volunteers and written informed consent was obtained prior to participation. Personal data were anonymized and handled in accordance with institutional policies.

On-Skin Flexibility and Adhesion

Electrospun patches were cut into $10 \times 30\text{ mm}$ strips and applied on a healthy volunteer's index finger, which was washed with a gentle, residue-free soap, rinsed, then lightly dabbed with a lint-free wipe so the skin stayed just a bit moist (to mimic wound-margin hydration). Each patch was pressed onto the damp area for 30 s, then the finger was straightened and bent to roughly 45° and 90° (holding each for 10 s) to watch for wrinkles, lifting, or cracks. Finally, we peeled the patch off at a 90° angle and noted whether it came away cleanly or tore.

Statistical Analysis

Data are presented as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). Group differences were evaluated with a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). When the overall ANOVA was significant, Tukey's honestly significant difference test was applied for all pair-wise comparisons, where P-values < 0.05 were considered statistically significant.

Results and discussion

Fiber Morphology

The surface morphology of the electrospun nanofibers was analyzed using SEM, to compare non-crosslinked and crosslinked nanofibers, as shown in Figure 2A. All samples demonstrated a continuous and bead-free fibrous structure prior to crosslinking, reflecting the success of the optimized electrospinning parameters in producing uniform and stable nanofiber mats. The incorporation of natural extracts (hawthorn and dragon blood) did not significantly disrupt fiber formation but did influence fiber diameter and distribution. P0 (control) showed smooth, uniform fibers with relatively consistent diameters, with an average fiber diameter of $313 \pm 83\text{ nm}$. PH, which included hawthorn extract, exhibited slightly thinner and

more heterogeneous fibers, with an average fiber diameter of 263 ± 74 nm. This is attributed to the initial low viscosity of the hawthorn extract, which appeared to reduce the overall solution viscosity, a change that was noticeable during both mixing and loading into the syringe. The decreased viscosity promoted greater jet stretching during electrospinning, due to the reduced resistance to elongation forces in the electrospinning jet, leading to thinner fiber formation[42]. In contrast, PD, containing dragon blood extract, maintained a similar fiber diameter distribution to P0, with an average fiber diameter of 325 ± 89 nm. Despite increasing the total water content, the overall viscosity of the PD solution remained relatively stable, likely due to the higher intrinsic viscosity or thicker consistency of the dragon blood extract, which helped preserve the polymer network's integrity during spinning. In PHD-M and PHD-Co, where both extracts were incorporated either as a mixture or via co-electrospinning, the fibers were noticeably thinner. In both groups, the average fiber diameter shifted to lower ranges, including 278 ± 95 nm for PHD-M and 239 ± 66 nm for PHD-Co. This reduction in fiber diameter is attributed to the higher amount of liquid extract added. Each extract was used at 70% of the polymer mass, and since the polymer concentration was 15% w/v, this corresponds to roughly 10.5% v/v. In the PHD-M and Co-spun groups, both extracts were included, effectively doubling the extract volume to approximately 21% v/v. This substantial addition effectively reduced the viscosity of the spinning solution, resulting in finer and more variable fibers in PHD-M and PHD-Co.

Post-crosslinking SEM images reveal significant morphological changes across all groups. The structure appeared less porous and more connected, particularly in the patches that were loaded with the extracts. GA crosslinking caused shrinkage, partial fusion, and densification of fibers due to network stabilization and moisture loss during fixation. This fusing behavior is consistent with the mechanism described by Rahmani et al [43], where the exposure to GA vapor in a humid environment causes the hydrophilic PVA fibers to swell and merge at contact points. This inter-fiber fusion is critical for enhancing the dimensional stability of the mat, as it prevents the structural collapse often seen in non-crosslinked fibers upon hydration. Notably, in PHD-M, the fibrous structure transitioned into a web-like or film-like matrix with reduced individual fiber distinction, suggesting stronger phase interactions due to the higher concentration of the extracts. This morphological transition is consistent with other studies reported in PVA and pectin electrospun systems[44], where exposure to crosslinking vapor induces a plasticization effect. This process promotes polymer chain diffusion at fiber intersections, resulting in a fused, continuous network. These transformations are attributed to GA vapor crosslinking, which forms covalent bonds primarily between hydroxyl groups of PVA and PEC through acetal bridges[45]. The interaction may also partially involve PVP, although it has fewer reactive groups. Additionally, the presence of polyphenolic compounds in the extracts[46] can enhance crosslinking by introducing more functional groups[47] and interacting with GA itself, leading to intensified morphological changes in the patches, including the extracts.

Chemical Properties

FTIR spectroscopy was employed to elucidate the chemical composition and confirm the successful integration and crosslinking of the electrospun P0 nanofibers, and the curves are presented in Figure 2B-C. The FTIR spectrum of the electrospun PVA-PVP-PEC fibers revealed distinct absorption bands corresponding to the functional groups of each polymer component (Figure 2B). For PVA, exhibited a broad O-H stretching vibration around 3280 cm^{-1} , indicative of hydroxyl groups, along with peaks at 2917 cm^{-1} (CH_2 asymmetric stretching) and 1081 cm^{-1} (C-O stretching). These findings align with previous studies reporting similar characteristic peaks for PVA-based nanofibers where broad O-H stretching band around $3200\text{--}3400\text{ cm}^{-1}$, C-H stretching vibrations near $2900\text{--}2950\text{ cm}^{-1}$, and characteristic carbonyl and C-O stretching bands attributed to the polysaccharide component, confirming the coexistence of PVA and pectin within the nanofibrous matrix[48]. For PVP, prominent peaks near 2950 cm^{-1} (asymmetric C-H stretching)

and approximately 1640 cm^{-1} appeared, which corresponded to the C=O stretching of the pyrrolidone ring. Additional peaks at 1460 and 1295 cm^{-1} were attributed to C–N bending and stretching vibrations, respectively. For PEC, characteristic peaks between 1639 cm^{-1} and 1737 cm^{-1} appeared, which are associated with C=O stretching vibrations, and around 1059 cm^{-1} for C–O stretching, consistent with literature reports on PEC-containing composites. The FTIR spectrum of the P0 fibers revealed that the majority of the spectral features closely resembled those of PVA, which is expected due to its predominance (70%) in the fiber composition. The major peak corresponding to PVP was recorded around 1650 cm^{-1} , while the characteristic absorption for PEC appeared near 1700 cm^{-1} and approximately 1020 cm^{-1} .

Post-crosslinking with GA, a new absorption band emerged around 1130 cm^{-1} (Figure 2B), attributed to C–O–C stretching vibrations, signifying the formation of acetal linkages between GA and the hydroxyl groups of PVA[45]. A reduction in the intensity of the O–H stretching band ($\sim 3280\text{ cm}^{-1}$) was also noted, suggesting the consumption of hydroxyl groups during the crosslinking reaction, further corroborating the formation of acetal bonds. These spectral changes confirm the successful chemical crosslinking of the nanofibers, enhancing their structural integrity and stability, which are critical for biomedical applications such as wound dressings. Subsequent characterizations were therefore performed exclusively on the crosslinked scaffolds to ensure the evaluation of the final, stabilized form of the material.

Mechanical Properties

The mechanical properties of the electrospun patches, assessed in terms of tensile strength and elongation at break, are presented in Figures 2D and E, respectively. The P0 patch exhibited a tensile strength of approximately $5.3 \pm 0.25\text{ MPa}$ and an elongation at break of $7.1 \pm 0.35\%$. The incorporation of hawthorn extract (PH) slightly enhanced tensile strength to $\sim 6.8 \pm 0.22\text{ MPa}$ ($p < 0.05$), while the dragon blood-loaded patch (PD) significantly increased the tensile strength to $\sim 7.7 \pm 0.46\text{ MPa}$. This enhancement is likely due to the cohesive and adhesive nature of dragon blood [49], owing to the phenolic groups of DB which are capable of forming hydrogen bonds[50]. In contrast, PHD-M and PHD-Co, which incorporate both HE and DB, showed a modest drop in tensile strengths to approximately $\sim 6.4 \pm 0.9\text{ MPa}$ and $6.7 \pm 1\text{ MPa}$, respectively. Although these values are slightly lower than the DB-only formulation (PD), they remained higher than the pristine P0 patch. This is attributed to the abundant polyphenolic groups in Dragon's blood, which are able to establish hydrogen-bond cross-links with the hydroxyl-rich PVA/PVP chains, a mechanism that is well-known to raise the cohesive strength of PVA-based networks [51].

Elongation behavior exhibited a different trend: both P0 and PH demonstrated limited ductility with $\sim 7.1 \pm 0.3$ and $7.1 \pm 0.4\%$ elongation at break respectively, while PD showed a moderate increase ($\sim 8.9 \pm 1.5\%$). Notably, PHD-M exhibited a significant increase in elongation ($\sim 12.2 \pm 2.7\%$, $p < 0.01$). PHD-Co also showed improved flexibility ($\sim 9 \pm 0.3\%$) compared to the control. The tensile strengths observed in this study (5.5–7.8 MPa) are comparable to those of electrospun pure PVA nanofibers, which have reported values of around 5.59 MPa [52]. However, the elongation at break is substantially lower than the 50.17% observed for PVA alone. On the other hand, pure PVP nanofibers have been reported to exhibit a tensile strength of $2.30 \pm 0.2\text{ MPa}$ and an elongation at break of $9.10 \pm 0.2\%$ [53], indicating that the presence of PVP in our blend may contribute to the lower elongation. Among the formulations studied, PD, which showed the highest degree of crystallinity ($\approx 40.3\%$), also exhibited the highest tensile strength ($\sim 7.8\text{ MPa}$), whereas PHD-M, with the lowest crystallinity ($\approx 30.5\%$), attained the highest elongation at break ($\sim 12\%$)—highlighting how densely packed crystalline domains reinforce stiffness and strength while more amorphous regions promote ductility. This behavior is characteristic of semicrystalline polymers, where an increase in crystallinity restricts chain mobility and elevates tensile performance while reduced crystallinity enhances flexibility and elongation[54].

Figure 2. (A): SEM images of the fiber with fiber diameter distribution as-spun and after the GA crosslinking, (B): The FTIR spectra of the PVA, PVP, and PEC, and their blend as electrospun patch (PVA-PVP-PEC), (C): the FTIR comparison of the patches post-crosslinking, (D and E): Mechanical properties including tensile strength and elongation at break of the fiber patches, (F): water contact angle comparison of the patches. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$.

Water Contact Angle

The electrospun nanofibrous patches exhibited tailored surface wettability, a critical feature for maintaining skin hydration in wound care applications. As shown in Figure 2F, all formulations demonstrated significant hydrophilicity, supporting their potential to reduce transepidermal water loss[55]. Pristine P0 displayed a

WCA of $31.9^\circ \pm 1.2^\circ$, while single-extract variants, PH (hawthorn-loaded) and PD (dragon's blood-loaded), showed similar values ($31.6^\circ \pm 0.9^\circ$ and $31.7^\circ \pm 1.1^\circ$, respectively), indicating that individual extract loading did not significantly alter surface wettability. However, the dual-extract formulations exhibited markedly improved hydrophilicity. PHD-M showed the lowest WCA ($26.1^\circ \pm 0.8^\circ$), and PHD-Co also demonstrated enhanced wettability ($29.2^\circ \pm 1.0^\circ$), both significantly lower than single-extract or pristine samples ($p < 0.05$). This enhancement is likely due to the synergistic presence of hydrophilic functional groups from both extracts, increasing water affinity at the fiber surface. Improved wettability not only supports hydration but also contributes to better patch-skin interface interactions and moisture retention—essential attributes for promoting a favorable healing environment.

Thermal Properties

Thermal analysis is essential for evaluating the viscoelastic behavior, mechanical stability, and thermal transitions of wound dressing materials, as it helps predict their structural integrity during storage, sterilization, and application. A comprehensive summary of all calorimetric, dynamic mechanical, thermogravimetric and crystallinity data is given in Table 1. The full DSC thermograms, TGA traces, and DMA plots are provided in the Supporting Information (Figures S1A-D). The lower glass transition, T_{g1} ($45.6\text{--}51.0^\circ\text{C}$), is attributed to the PEC phase[56], which is relatively narrow since the weight fraction is 10wt % PEC. The higher glass transition, T_{g2} ($100.8\text{--}123.5^\circ\text{C}$), corresponds to the amorphous PVA–PVP–PEC network, falling between the reported T_g range for pure PVA and PVP. Typically, PVA exhibits a T_g in the range of $75\text{--}85^\circ\text{C}$ [57], PVP is reported to have a higher T_g , often around $160\text{--}175^\circ\text{C}$ [58]. This observed T_g is higher than that of pure PVA and PEC, and relatively close to that of high molecular weight PVP. This suggests that the high molecular weight PVP (1300 KDa), despite being only 20% of the polymer blend, exerts a dominant influence on the overall glass transition of the composite. This influence is attributed to the increased chain entanglement and reduced chain mobility associated with very long polymer chains[59], which require significantly more energy (and thus higher temperature) to undergo segmental motion compared to the lower molecular weight PVA and PEC. A similar intermediate glass transition has been reported for PVA/PVP blends[60], where the presence of PVP significantly elevates the T_g of the composite due to restricted chain mobility and increased intermolecular interactions within the amorphous phase. However, $\tan\delta$ curves (Figure S1D), where the peak indicates the T_g , revealed the thermal transitions of the electrospun patches at $144\text{--}153^\circ\text{C}$, nearly 20°C above the calorimetric T_{g2} . Higher T_g from DMA compared to DSC was also reported for semicrystalline polymers[61], due to the different detection modes of the two techniques. In DSC, the glass transition is registered as a heat-capacity step under a continuous, near-equilibrium heating ramp, whereas in DMA, it is detected only when polymer segments can respond to an oscillatory stress. As a result, a higher temperature is required for segmental mobility to match the applied frequency, yielding an elevated T_g in DMA measurement. The incorporation of Hawthorn extract and Dragon's blood, individually and combined, resulted in minimal shifts, suggesting these extracts, at their given concentrations, had limited plasticizing or anti-plasticizing effects on the overall polymer matrix.

The melting temperatures (T_m) of all patches were consistently recorded within a narrow range of $210\text{--}214^\circ\text{C}$, which is within the melting temperature range of PVA[62]. The melting enthalpy (ΔH_m) varied from 42.30 to 55.87 J g^{-1} , which gives X_c values of 43.6% (PHD-M) up to 57.6% (PD). The notably higher X_c in PD reflects the phenolics in dragon blood acting as heterogeneous nucleation sites that promote more extensive, well-ordered PVA lamellae during crystallization[63].

Table 1. A summary of the thermal properties of the patches. T_g is the glass transition temperature; T_m is the melting temperature; ΔH_m is the melting enthalpy; X_c represents the degree of crystallinity.

Sample	T_{g1} DSC (°C)	T_{g2} DSC (°C)	T_m (°C)	Δh_m ($J g^{-1}$)	X_c (%)	Residue at 800 °C (%)	T_g DMA (°C)
P0	47.8	104.4	212.52	49.36	50.9	0.1 \geq	151.4
PH	45.6	100.8	210.11	44.42	45.8	0.1 \geq	144.7
PD	50.7	115.4	210.11	55.87	57.6	0.1 \geq	153.5
PHD-M	51.0	115.3	214.67	42.29	43.6	0.1 \geq	151.0
PHD-CO	50.9	123.5	212.59	47.13	48.6	0.1 \geq	150.6

T_g is the glass transition temperature; T_m is the melting temperature; ΔH_m is the melting enthalpy; X_c represents the degree of crystallinity.

Swelling ratio

The swelling behavior of the electrospun patches was evaluated over a 72-hour period in distilled water to assess their fluid uptake capacity, an essential feature for wound dressings that must absorb exudate while maintaining a moist environment [33], and the results are presented in Figure 3 (A). All patches exhibited rapid water absorption, swelling to approximately 300–380% of their dry weight within the first 15 min, followed by a gradual deswelling phase over the next 72 h. The patch containing hawthorn extract (PH) showed the highest peak swelling (~390%), followed by PD and PHD-M (~350%), while the co-spun formulation had the lowest swelling capacity (~310%). This behavior mirrors observations in pure PVA electrospun mats, which swell to ~400% due to their high surface-area-to-volume ratio and abundance of hydrophilic –OH groups, compared to only ~140% for cast PVA films[64]. The enhanced swelling of HE-loaded fibers likely arises from the hydrophilic polyphenols in hawthorn extract that increase the water affinity of the fiber matrix. Moreover, after crosslinking, the electrospun patches underwent fiber deformation and exhibited a smaller average fiber diameter compared to other samples, which further contributes to their higher water uptake. Electrospun patches with different fiber diameters exhibit varying water uptake and swelling properties. Patches with thinner fibers generally have lower water uptake and slower absorption rates compared to thicker fibers[65]. High initial swelling is beneficial for rapid exudate absorption, while the sustained, controlled deswelling helps maintain a moist wound environment over the days, promoting re-epithelialization and reducing dressing change frequency. The slight decline in swelling ratio over time may not indicate reduced water affinity of the patches but could instead reflect polymer chain breakdown and associated mass loss under the testing conditions.

Degradation Study

The degradation behavior of the electrospun nanofibrous patches, evaluated by monitoring mass loss in PBS over 72 h, revealed distinct trends influenced by formulation. As shown in Figure 3B, the PHD-Co and PH patches exhibited the most rapid degradation, retaining approximately 39% and 30% of their original mass, respectively. In contrast, PHD-M, PD, and pristine P0 retained between 50% and 55% of their initial mass, indicating slower degradation kinetics. The accelerated degradation observed in PH may be attributed to its higher swelling capacity, which enhances water penetration and facilitates hydrolytic chain scission. This relationship between swelling and degradation is well-documented for hydrophilic polymeric systems, where increased fluid uptake accelerates the breakdown of the polymer. Additionally,

the dual-extract composition in PHD-Co, despite its lower swelling, may contribute to reduced structural stability due to altered fiber morphology and inter-polymer interactions. These results indicate that both the chemical nature of incorporated extracts and fiber architecture significantly influence the degradation profile, an important consideration for tailoring patch longevity in wound healing applications. Moreover, the influence of blend composition and polymer compatibility may also contribute to structural instability over time, as discussed in a study by Liu et al., where mixing PVA with other hydrophilic components enhanced both the degradation and swelling responses[66].

Drug Release Study

The release profiles of DB and HE from the electrospun patches demonstrate a consistent upward trend over the 120-hour duration, highlighting similar release behaviors for each antifungal agent (Figure 3C - D). Overall, HE exhibited a higher cumulative release, reaching about 75% at 120 h, while DB release was lower, plateauing around 50%. This difference, with DB exhibiting slower release, can likely be linked to the enhanced structural stability provided by DB incorporation, as evidenced in the mechanical properties, which improved the tensile strength of the patches. The release profile of HE differed across formulations, where the patch containing HE alone (PH), showed the highest release, reaching nearly 75% by 120 h. In comparison, PHD-M and PHD-Co released lower amounts of HE (about 58% and 65%, respectively), with PHD-M showing the lowest release, likely due to the stronger matrix stability when combined with DB. In contrast, DB displayed a very consistent release pattern across PD, PHD-M, and PHD-Co, all reaching around 50% at 120 h, suggesting that DB release is largely unaffected by the presence of HE. The PHD-M samples are particularly interesting because both HE and DB showed very similar release trend and levels over time and after 120 h (~58% and ~50%, respectively). This balance indicates a more synchronized release profile, which may be beneficial by ensuring that both agents are available at comparable levels over time, potentially enhancing their combined antifungal effectiveness. Mechanistically, this biphasic profile, characterized by an initial surface-driven burst followed by sustained release, aligns with Fickian diffusion behavior typical of swelling-controlled PVA matrices[67]. This suggests the release is governed by drug diffusion through the hydrated polymer network, ensuring immediate antimicrobial action followed by prolonged therapeutic delivery.

Figure 3. (A): The trend line comparison of the swelling ratio of the patches in different time intervals, (B): Degradation behavior shown as remaining mass (%) over 72 h; (C): Cumulative release profile of hawthorn; (D): Cumulative release profile of dragon blood.

Antifungal Activity

All electrospun patches demonstrated fungistatic activity against *C. albicans*. The disk diffusion test showed that patches have an antifungal zone ranging from 14-18 mm which indicates moderate antifungal activity in comparison with the control disks consisting of tissue culture polystyrene of the same size as the patch samples, which show no zones at all (Figure 4A). In the fungicidal assay, P0 showed only a modest reduction in viable cells (\log_{10} reduction ≈ 0.8). Incorporation of HE (PH) or DB (PD) led to reductions of about 0.2 and 0.05, respectively, respectively. In contrast, both dual-loaded samples, PHD-M and PHD-Co, achieved complete inhibition of fungal growth, corresponding to a \log_{10} reduction greater than 7; relative to the untreated control (Table 2). These results clearly demonstrate that patches containing both HE and DB have a markedly stronger antifungal effect compared with the bioactive agents alone. The fungicidal performance of PHD-M and PHD-Co indicates that the combination of HE and DB leads to complete suppression of *C. albicans*, highlighting the advantage of dual loading. Such a balanced and complementary effect makes dual-loaded patches promising candidates for antifungal applications.

Table 2. Fungicidal activity of electrospun patches against *Candida albicans*. Data are shown as colony-forming units (CFU) after 2 h exposure in YEPD medium and the corresponding \log_{10} reduction (mean of three replicates). A log reduction ≥ 3 was considered fungicidal. Both dual-loaded formulations (PHD-M and PHD-Co) achieved complete inhibition of fungal growth (log reduction > 7).

Patch	Treated cells Mean \pm SD (CFU-10 ⁶)	Growth control (CFU-10 ⁷)	Log reduction
P0	1.46 \pm 0.06	1	0.8
PH	6.43 \pm 0.15		0.2
PD	9 \pm 1		0.05
PHD-M	0		>7
PHD-Co	0		>7

Cytotoxicity Study

Biocompatibility of the electrospun patches was assessed using an indirect MTT assay with L929 fibroblasts, and the results are shown in Figure 4. All formulations showed cell viability values above the 70% threshold (dashed black line), confirming the absence of cytotoxicity and the general biocompatibility of the patches. The P0 patch demonstrated a cell viability of approximately 87%, indicating minimal interference with cellular metabolic activity. The addition of hawthorn extract (PH) yielded a comparable viability of ~85%, while the dragon blood-containing patch (PD) showed the highest viability at ~93%. This improvement may be attributed to the antioxidant and cytoprotective properties of dragon blood, which could mitigate oxidative stress and enhance cell survival. The blended extract formulations, PHD-M and PHD-Co, also maintained viabilities within the acceptable range, at ~84% and ~80%, respectively. The slightly reduced values compared to PD may reflect synergistic or antagonistic interactions between the polyphenolic compounds in the two extracts, which could transiently affect cellular metabolic activity. Nevertheless, all patches were classified as non-cytotoxic, and no significant loss of viability was detected.

Figure 4. (A): Inhibition zones of electrospun patches against *Candida albicans*; the tissue culture polystyrene plate of the same size as the patch sample served as a control (B): The cytotoxicity results of the patches in the presence of L929 fibroblast cells. The dashed line indicates the 70% cytotoxicity threshold according to ISO10993-5.

The Water Vapor Transmission Rate (WVTR)

Since only the dual-loaded patches (PHD-M and PHD-Co) exhibited fungicidal activity against *C. albicans* (Table 2), we selected these formulations for further investigation to reduce redundancy and focus on the most efficacious candidates. WVTR is a critical parameter for evaluating the breathability and moisture control capacity of wound dressings and transdermal patches. The WVTR of a wound dressing directly regulates the wound microenvironment by balancing moisture: too high WVTR can lead to dehydration of the wound surface, whereas too low WVTR may trap exudate and cause maceration of surrounding tissue[68]. An appropriate WVTR helps maintain a moist environment that supports cell proliferation and wound healing, while preventing both excessive fluid accumulation and desiccation. In this study, the WVTR of two electrospun patch formulations—PHD-M and PHD-Co, was assessed over a 72-hour period. At 24 h, the PHD-M patches showed higher WVTR (mean ≈ 856 g/m²/day) compared to PHD-Co (mean ≈ 750 g/m²/day) ($p < 0.01$), suggesting that the modified formulation allowed greater moisture vapor flux. Commercial dressings such as Tegaderm and Opsite exhibit WVTR values around 794–839 g/m²/day for moisture release from the wound outward, and 846–862 g/m²/day for vapor ingress from the external environment, indicating their comparable and balanced moisture permeability characteristics[69]. Several studies on wound dressing materials have also reported WVTR values in ranges consistent with those observed here. For example, electrospun poly(L-lactide-co- ϵ -caprolactone)-based composite fibers demonstrated WVTR values around 557 g/m²/day [70] and values similar to commercial dressings such as Tegaderm™ (~ 792 g/m²/day) under comparable conditions, indicating that engineered electrospun dressings can achieve moisture transmission rates within practical and clinically relevant ranges. Similarly, chitosan-based nanobiohybrid membranes for wound applications exhibited WVTR values in the range of approximately 690–860 g/m²/day, supporting the notion that WVTR values in the range of 750–856 g/m²/day (as seen for PHD-Co and PHD-M) are aligned with other advanced wound dressing systems designed in the literature[71]. Commercial wound dressings have been shown to exhibit a wide range of WVTR values (from 75 to several thousand g/m²/day)[72], and values up to ~ 2000 – 2500 g m⁻² day⁻¹ are

still considered consistent with moist wound healing without excessive dehydration. Furthermore, the patches retained a relatively consistent WVTR over time, with slight reduction values at 48 h and 72 h, respectively. This indicates sustained moisture management performance across prolonged exposure.

Skin Hydration

The electrospun nanofibrous patches developed in this study demonstrated significant efficacy in sustaining skin hydration over a 6-hour period. As illustrated in Figure 5, both selected formulations significantly increased skin moisture levels after 3 h and 6 h, compared to the cellulose patch control ($p < 0.05$), confirming their hydrating potential. This effect is attributed to the hydrophilic PVA–PVP–PEC polymer blend, which contains abundant hydroxyl and carbonyl groups capable of forming hydrogen bonds with water molecules[73]. These interactions enable the patches to absorb and retain moisture, mimicking the natural hydration function of healthy skin. Additionally, fibrous architecture acts as a semi-occlusive barrier, limiting transepidermal water loss and further promoting moisture retention, since hydrogel-based dressings are known for accelerating wound repair[74]. While wound bed naturally creates a moist environment, the patches could retain and increase the moisture on the skin to around 40% after 6 h of application. This superior performance suggests a synergistic performance in promoting efficient wound healing. Adequate hydration enhances cell migration, like fibroblasts and keratinocytes, which are crucial for tissue repair and wound closure[75], facilitates key enzymatic activity and supports collagen synthesis, all of which are essential for wound healing[76,77]. Moist can also reduce pain by keeping nerve endings hydrated and minimizing the formation of dry, scab-like tissue that can cause discomfort [78]. Modern wound dressings, therefore, aim not only to protect the wound but also to retain moisture and create a favorable microenvironment for healing. Altogether, these results underscore the potential of the dual extract electrospun patches as multifunctional wound dressings, combining hydration retention, surface wettability, and antifungal activity, essential features for promoting effective healing and improving comfort during wear. However, it is important to acknowledge that this study was conducted on a relatively small number of volunteers ($n=7$). Also, the tests were performed on healthy, intact skin rather than compromised barriers or active Atopic Dermatitis lesions. Consequently, these findings primarily validate the material's biocompatibility and hydration efficacy, serving as a proof-of-concept for future clinical studies. However, further studies with larger and more diverse sample populations, involving patients with compromised skin barriers are recommended to further validate the statistical robustness and long-term efficacy of these patches in clinical settings.

The mechanical properties of wound dressings in terms of retaining their shape, resisting deformation during use, and mirroring the flexibility of native skin are a crucial consideration that must be addressed[79]. Both PHD-M and PHD-Co adhered smoothly to the lightly damp skin and retained excellent flexibility under bending at 45° and 90°, with neither showing any cracks, indicating good attachment and flexibility on the skin. PHD-M remained fully conformal while PHD-Co displayed only minor edge lift, which can be attributed to elongation properties. The superior on-skin bending performance of PHD-M correlates with its higher elongation at break (~12%) versus PHD-Co (~9%) in tensile tests, confirming that a homogeneous mix of polymer and extracts enhances ductility and skin-interface compliance. Upon 90° peel, both patches peeled cleanly and intact, though no residue remained. Notably, once applied to the humidified skin surface, both hydrogel patches became highly transparent, which can facilitate visual monitoring of the wound site while maintaining semi-permeable, moisture-retaining properties. This behavior aligns with the key advantages of modern film dressings, the most important of which include transparency, flexibility, and semi-permeability. They do not limit mobility, and they enable observation of healing progress while protecting against fungal infections. PHD-M tolerated estimated surface strains > 30% without fracture. Together, these data identify PHD-M as the lead formulation for articulated-site

wound care, combining transparency for wound inspection, flexibility for joint movement, and balanced adhesion for atraumatic removal. Overall, PHD-M emerges as the superior articulated-site wound dressing, offering transparency for monitoring, flexibility for movement, gentle adhesion for clean removal, and a simpler single-solution electrospinning process.

Figure 5. (A): The water vapor transmission rate of the PHD-M and PHD-Co after 24, 48 and 72h of applying on skin, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.0001$; (B) skin moisture levels of the PHD-M and PHD-Co after 3h and 6h of applying on skin; (C) Deformation resistance of the PHD-M and PHD-Co patches applied on skin; D: a demonstration of the skin hydration test on the forearm

Conclusion

This study successfully developed multifunctional electrospun PVA-PVP-PEC patches loaded with plant-based bioactive extracts (hawthorn extract and dragon's blood) through optimized single-solution and co-spinning processes, yielding uniform nanofibers. The structural integrity was further improved by crosslinking the patches, targeting the development of biofunctional patches. The mechanical tests showed that DB increased tensile strength, while the mixed formulation (PHD-M) provided the highest flexibility. The patches swelled rapidly, degraded in a controlled way, and released the plant extracts in a sustained manner. HE showed a higher overall release (~75%), while DB released more slowly (~50%); yet combined together in the mixed formulation (PHD-M), the two agents displayed a balanced release profile. All patches were non-cytotoxic and showed potent antifungal activity, with dual-loaded formulations achieving complete inhibition of *C. albicans*. The patches also demonstrated WVTR values comparable to commercial dressings and significantly retained the skin moisture after 6 h of application on the skin. Taken together, these findings identify PHD-M as the lead formulation, combining balanced bio-active agent release, strong antifungal performance, high flexibility, transparency for wound monitoring, and gentle adhesion. PHD-M therefore holds strong potential for future clinical studies in the treatment of atopic dermatitis and related skin conditions.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Supporting Information

Supplementary figures, including thermal analyses (DSC, TGA, DMA) and WVTR setup photograph (DOCX).

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